

Regulation of Egg Activation in *Drosophila*

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Abstract

Egg activation in *Drosophila* describes a series of events that signify the transition of mature oocyte to embryo. This includes completion of meiosis, destabilization of maternally deposited mRNA transcripts, and cortical microtubule reorganization. This project investigates the poorly understood upstream regulation of transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization to better understand eukaryotic embryogenesis. Many of the events of egg activation are regulated by the Anaphase Promoting Complex/Cyclosome (APC/C), a multi-subunit E3 ubiquitin ligase which facilitates the metaphase to anaphase transition in mitosis and meiosis. Transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization are both presumed to be APC/C dependent; however, this is still an area of ongoing investigation. The APC/C, activated by Cyclin-dependent kinase 1 (Cdk1) mediated phosphorylation and binding of Cort and Fzy subunits, ubiquitinates substrates which are subsequently degraded by the proteasome. We propose a model based on previous work for transcript destabilization that involves Cdk1-Cyclin B3 activating APC/C^{Cort/Fzy}, which subsequently degrades Cyclin B3, causing a drop in Cdk1 activity. This drop in Cdk1 activity allows an enzyme known as the PAN GU kinase complex to transition to an active, unphosphorylated state. Active PAN GU kinase can then phosphorylate well characterized downstream targets which mediate transcript destabilization. Cortical microtubule reorganization, although likely APC/C dependent, remains poorly understood. This project employs mutant alleles and RNAi knockdown to investigate Cyclin B3, Cort, Fzy, and APC/C roles, assessing transcript destabilization using qRT-PCR and cortical microtubule reorganization via immunostaining. Our data suggests that Fzy is required for transcript destabilization. Other components are still in the process of investigation.

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Table of Contents

Abstract.....	2
1. Introduction	5
1.1 Cell Division	5
1.2 Cyclin Dependent Kinases	5
1.3 Cyclins	6
1.4 The APC/C, Fzy, and Cort	7
1.5 Egg Activation	9
1.6 Objectives	12
2. Materials and Methods	14
2.1. Gal4-UAS System	14
2.2. Crosses	14
2.3. Sample Preparation for Western Blot	16
2.4. Western Blot Protocol	16
2.5. Bacterial Transformation and Plasmid Isolation	17
2.6. Restriction Digest	18
2.7. Embryo Collection	18
2.8. RNA Extraction	18
2.9. cDNA Synthesis	19
2.10. qRT-PCR	19
2.11. Methanol Fixation of Embryos	19
2.12. Immunostaining of Methanol Fixed Embryos	20
2.13. Formaldehyde Fixation of Embryos	20
2.14. Immunostaining of Formaldehyde Fixed Embryos	21
3. Results	22
3.1. Fzy Knockdown	22
3.2. APC/C Knockdown	23
3.3. Non-Degradable Cyclin B3	24
3.4. <i>cort;cycB3</i> Double Mutant	27
3.5. Microtubule Reorganization of <i>cort</i> Mutant to Determine Best Technique	27
4. Discussion	29
4.1. Fzy Knockdown	29
4.2. APC/C Knockdown	29
4.3. Non-Degradable Cyclin B3	30
4.4. <i>cort;cycB3</i> Double Mutant	32
4.5. Determination of Best Technique for Microtubule Staining	33
4.6. Conclusions and Additional Future Steps	33
Statement of Contribution	35
References.....	36

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Cell Division

Meiosis and mitosis are the two types of cellular divisions fundamental to all multicellular eukaryotes. The mechanisms governing mitosis and meiosis are under tight regulation, although meiotic regulation is less understood. Mitosis consists of a single round of cellular division that produces two genetically identical diploid daughter cells, whereas meiosis involves two successive divisions yielding four haploid gametes of different genetic composition. The first meiotic division involves separation of homologous chromosomes, whereas the second meiotic division involves separation of sister chromatids, analogous to mitosis. Mitosis is how complex multicellular organisms with differentiated cells arise from a single zygote to form complex organisms and is also largely involved in repair of damaged tissues. Meiosis is a mechanism that allows for sexual reproduction in eukaryotes, allowing for genetic diversity via recombination of maternal and paternal genes, creating genetically unique offspring.

1.2 Cyclin-dependent Kinases

All phases of the cell cycle, including cellular divisions, are intricately regulated by various cyclin-dependent kinases (Cdks). Cdks are serine/threonine kinases that rely on binding of cyclins to expose their active site (Ding et al., 2020). Cdks can bind to different cyclins, leading to different substrate specificity and ensuring coordinated progression throughout the cell cycle (Minshull et al., 1990). Cdk1 is a well conserved enzyme across eukaryotes that is necessary for mitotic and meiotic cellular divisions, hence also referred to as M-Cdk. Cyclin A, Cyclin B, and Cyclin B3 all interact with Cdk1. In addition to cyclin binding, two other criteria are necessary for Cdk1 to be fully activated: Cdc25 phosphatase mediated dephosphorylation of inhibitory phosphorylated sites on Cdk1 and

phosphorylation on Cdk1's T-loop mediated by Cdk7. (Gavet & Pines, 2010; Merrick et al., 2008; Sur & Agrawal, 2016).

The activity of Cdk1 activity orchestrates precise progression through cellular divisions. In both mitosis and meiosis, Cdk1 phosphorylates nuclear lamins and nuclear pore complexes to trigger nuclear envelope breakdown (NEB). NEB is a crucial initiating step of cellular division which allows cytosolic proteins to interact with nuclear contents and vice versa. Additionally, Cdk1 phosphorylates the condensin complex required for chromosome condensation in prophase (Abe et al., 2011). Cdk1 also phosphorylates a crucial cell cycle regulator, the anaphase promoting complex/cyclosome (APC/C). The APC/C is discussed in detail in later paragraphs.

1.3 Cyclins

Cyclins comprise a protein family known for their interaction with various Cdks. Structurally, they share a defined feature known as the cyclin box, a domain consisting of approximately 100 amino acid residues which form five alpha-helix secondary structures. (Malumbres, 2014). Cyclins were first discovered by Evans et al., 1983 due to their oscillating expression levels in dividing cells of sea urchin eggs.

Cyclin A, Cyclin B, and Cyclin B3 are all implicated with mitosis and appear to have partially redundant roles (Furuno et al., 1999; Swan & Schüpbach, 2005). In *Drosophila*, mutations to *cycA* are lethal whereas *cycB* mutants, which are sterile, and *cycB3*, which are female sterile, are viable (Reber, 2006; Bourouh & Swan, 2018; Jacobs et al., 1998). In contrast, both *cycA* and *cycB* mutants are lethal in vertebrates. *cycB* and *cycB3* double mutants are lethal in *Drosophila*, implicating an overlapping role in mitosis (Bourouh & Swan, 2018; Jacobs et al., 1998). All three mitotic cyclins get degraded during *Drosophila* mitosis, with Cyclin A usually being first, followed by Cyclin B and lastly Cyclin B3 (Swan

& Schüpbach, 2005). Cyclin A in complex to Cdk1 is directly involved in phosphorylation of nuclear lamins associated with NEB, Cyclin B also is involved in NEB when localized to the nucleus, along with other functions (Stiffler et al., 1999; Onischenko et al., 2005). Cyclin B3 is involved in chromosome condensation in prophase, mitotic progression, and anaphase onset via APC/C activation (Jacobs et al., 1998; Yuan & O'Farrell, 2015; Garrido et al., 2020).

The role of each cyclin in *Drosophila* meiosis appears to be more complex and again seemingly redundant in certain aspects. All three cyclins contribute to NEB, although cyclin A has the greatest contribution (Bourouh et al., 2016). Cyclin A is required early in meiosis I for proper homolog segregation (Bourouh et al., 2016). Cyclin B is necessary for the metaphase I arrest in mature oocytes, the timely advancement through the meiosis II, and proper spindle organization (Bourouh et al., 2016). Cyclin B3 in *Drosophila* meiosis is poorly understood, but Cyclin B3 activates the APC/C in meiosis (Garrido et al., 2020). Cyclin B3 is required for anaphase progression in meiosis I and II (Bourouh et al., 2016). In *cycB3* mutant females, defects in meiosis are seen only after metaphase I (Jacobs et al., 1998).

1.4 The APC/C, Fzy, and Cort

The anaphase promoting complex/cyclosome (APC/C) is a multi-subunit protein with E3 ubiquitin ligase enzymatic activity which facilitates the metaphase to anaphase transition in both mitosis and meiosis, although its role in meiosis is less characterized. Structurally, the APC/C is comprised of 13 subunits with a molecular weight of over 1 MDa, making it an incredibly large protein complex (McLean et al., 2011). The APC/C ubiquitinates substrates on lysine residues (Van Voorhis & Morgan, 2014). Following ubiquitination of substrates, they are recognized by the 26S proteasome for destruction where they are cleaved into peptide fragments (McLean et al., 2011).

With respect to the mitotic cell cycle, the APC/C becomes active during the metaphase to anaphase transition. The spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) is a complex of proteins and prevents premature activation of the APC/C, hence preventing improper or premature sister chromatid separation (McLean et al., 2011). One of the proteins of the SAC, Mad2, sequesters Cdc20 until proper mitotic spindle attachment has been achieved for all chromosomes in a cell. Cdc20 is one of two activating subunits of the APC/C, with the other one being Cdh1. APC/C^{Cdc20} is active predominantly in anaphase, where APC/C^{Cdh1} regulates Cdk activity after completion of anaphase. In addition to its activating subunit, the APC/C requires phosphorylation via Cdk1 to be active. The active APC/C has two relevant targets, Securin and M-phase cyclins. The APC/C recognizes a destruction box (D-box) motif on both cyclins and Securin substrates (Kraft et al., 2005).

Prior to APC/C activation, Securin is bound to the enzyme Separase; this interaction inhibits Separase (Luo & Tong, 2020). Securin ubiquitination mediated by the APC/C^{Cdc20} and subsequent destruction allows for freeing of Separase (Guo et al., 2015). Separase cleaves Scc1, which is a part of the cohesin protein complex holding sister chromatids together (Uhlmann, 2001). The cleavage of Scc1 permits the sister chromatid separation characteristic of anaphase (Uhlmann, 2001).

The other target of APC/C^{Cdc20} is the mitotic cyclins. This ubiquitination of the cyclins results in a decline of Cdk1 activity. Simply put, cyclins activate the machinery that causes its own destruction. This occurs in anaphase allowing migration of sister chromatids to their respective poles of the cell.

Interestingly, in *Drosophila* meiosis, there is no evidence suggesting the SAC for APC/C function is required for meiosis (Batiha & Swan, 2012). SAC mutants are viable and fertile. In *Drosophila*, the Cdc20 homologue is Fizzy (Fzy). Cortex (Cort) is another germline specific Cdc20 homologue in *Drosophila* females. Cort and Fzy have both distinct and redundant functions in meiosis. Both APC/C^{Cort} and APC/C^{Fzy} are implicated in meiotic cyclin A destruction, however APC/C^{Cort} has

much greater affinity (Vardy et al., 2009). APC/C^{Cort} ubiquitinates cyclin B associated with the spindle midzone, whereas APC/C^{Fzy} targets cyclin B localized to spindle microtubules in *Drosophila* meiosis (Swan and Schüpbach, 2007). *cort* mutants arrest in metaphase II, however the earliest requirement for Cort is chromosome segregation in anaphase I (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996). In contrast, *fzy* mutants arrest in anaphase II, however once again the earliest requirement of Fzy is in anaphase I (Swan and Schüpbach, 2007). Swan and Schüpbach, 2007 found that double mutants of *cort* and *fzy* arrest in metaphase II, furthermore suggesting distinct yet overlapping roles.

1.5 Egg Activation

Egg activation in *Drosophila* encompasses a series of events that signify the transition of mature oocyte to embryo. This includes completion of meiosis from their metaphase I arrest, microtubule reorganization around the cortex, degradation of certain maternally deposited messenger RNA (mRNA) transcripts, and increased protein translation in the absence of transcription (Theurkauf & Hawley, 1992; Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996; Hara et al., 2017; Tadros et al., 2003). Interestingly, fertilization is not a requirement for egg activation, and it is activation, not fertilization that alleviates meiotic arrest (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996; Mahowald et al., 1983). In *Drosophila*, egg activation typically occurs when the oocyte reaches the oviducts (Theurkauf & Hawley, 1992).

Destabilization of maternally deposited mRNA transcripts is a developmental process well conserved across the animal kingdom. This process occurs in the 3–5-hour time interval following eggs being laid. Transcripts are stable in the 0-2 hour time interval. During early embryogenesis, protein synthesis is dependent on maternally deposited transcripts rather than zygotic transcription to be translated into proteins (Tesarik, 2022). Maternal transcript deposition and destabilization has been observed in insects, mice, humans, and many other organisms (Preuss et al., 2012; Tora & Vincent, 2021; Tesarik, 2022). Egg activation alone is both necessary and sufficient to cause transcript

destabilization in *Drosophila* (Tadros et al., 2003). Approximately half of the *Drosophila* genome is represented in the maternally deposited mRNA transcripts (Tadros et al., 2007). Over 20% undergo destabilization following egg activation such that more than 1600 transcripts get degraded (Tadros et al., 2007).

The downstream components of the phenomenon of transcript destabilization in *Drosophila* are better established. Prior to egg activation and transcript destabilization, an enzyme known as the PAN GU (PNG) kinase complex is in a phosphorylated state due to high Cdk1 activity. Cdk1 specifically phosphorylates GNU, a subunit of the PNG complex which prevents interactions with the other subunits of the protein complex, hence rendering the enzyme inactive (Hara et al., 2017). Decreased Cdk1 activity as a consequence of meiosis completion following egg activation allows the PNG kinase complex to transition from an inhibited phosphorylated state to an active dephosphorylated state (Hara et al., 2017). The active PNG kinase complex can then phosphorylate Trailer Hitch (TRAL), a well conserved translational repressor (Hara et al., 2018). The phosphorylation of TRAL is inhibitory and thus TRAL becomes inactive. TRAL inhibition subsequently allows for translation of SMAUG, also referred to as SMG (Hara et al., 2018). Mature SMG protein is also a translational repressor which functions as an RNA binding protein. SMG binds to SMG Response Elements (SREs) located in the 3' untranslated region (UTR) of specific mRNA transcripts (Tadros et al., 2007). Once SMG is bound to SREs, it localizes CCR4/POP2/NOT deadenylase which consequently causes deadenylation of the 3' poly-A-tail of mRNA transcripts (Tadros et al., 2007; Semotok et al., 2005). The poly-A-tail normally protects the transcript from endogenous cytosolic exonucleases, therefore deadenylation allows for exonucleases to destroy the transcript (Semotok et al., 2005).

The upstream initiation of transcript destabilization is less understood. We propose that Cyclin B3 is both the critical activator and target of the APC/C required for transcript destabilization. Our lab's

hypothesized model, as described in Figure 1, involves Cyclin B3 being degraded via APC/C ubiquitination leading to a subsequent drop in Cdk1 activity. In other words, we think Cyclin B3 destruction following egg activation is necessary for transcript destabilization. Decreased Cdk1 activity would allow for PNG kinase to transition from an inhibited phosphorylated state to a catalytically active state. This active PNG kinase would then be able to function as described as described above. As previously mentioned, both Fzy and Cort are activating subunits of the APC/C. *cort* mutants fail to undergo transcript destabilization (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996; Lieberfarb et al., 1996; Boruouh, 2018). Previous preliminary data show that *fzy*, and the APC/C are required for transcript destabilization, whereas transcript destabilization does occur in *cycB3* mutants, which is all consistent with our model (Boruouh, 2018).

Figure 1. Proposed model for transcript destabilization. The model starts with Fzy, Cort and Cdk1 (in complex with its Cyclin B3 subunit) activating the APC/C. Following activation, the APC/C ubiquitinates the Cyclin B3 for degradation. The drop in Cyclin B3 levels consequently causes a reduction of Cdk1 activity. This reduction in Cdk1 activity allows for the PNG kinase complex to transition from an inhibited phosphorylated state to an active dephosphorylated state. PNG kinase activity ultimately leads to mRNA transcript destabilization via inhibitory phosphorylations of TRAL, a translational repressor, which consequently allows for SMAUG translation. SMAUG then recruits CCR4/POP2/NOT deadenylase, which ultimately leads to transcript destabilization.

Cortical microtubule reorganization is another phenomenon that occurs following egg activation.

Drosophila oocytes contains an elaborate microtubule network around the outer parts of the oocyte.

Following activation, these microtubules are disassembled and broken down (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996). This mechanism of this process is poorly understood. Both *cort* mutants and RNAi knockdown of APC1 subunit do not show this reorganization, rather the microtubule network is present following after activation (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996; Boruouh, 2018). Microtubule reorganization is not affected in *cycB3* mutants, and show a phenotype similar to wildtype (Boruouh, 2018).

1.6 Objectives

This study aims to gain insight into regulation of two main events of activation: maternally deposited mRNA transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization. We used a combination of mutant alleles and RNA interference mediated knockdown in the female germline to gain insight into the molecular regulation of these events.

Preliminary data from our lab shows that Fzy and the APC/C are both required transcript destabilization and the APC/C is required for cortical microtubule depolymerization (Boruouh, 2018). The first aim of this study was to replicate these experiments. Embryos with respective RNA knockdowns of Fzy and the APC/C were collected. The eggs were then either stained for microtubules or had relative mRNA levels examined using quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR). We expected these results to replicate the previous findings, therefore having very strong evidence that cortical microtubule reorganization and transcript destabilization is both Fzy and APC/C dependant, which coincides with our proposed model.

The second aim investigates the role of Cyclin B3 in these two events. With respect to transcript destabilization, we think Cyclin B3 is both the critical activator of the APC/C and the critical target for destruction. Firstly, we wanted to express a non-degradable form of Cyclin B3 in the female germline. This non-degradable Cyclin B3 was previously designed in our lab using site directed mutagenesis, and

will be referred to as Cyclin B3-d. The mutation occurs in the D-box of Cyclin B3, ultimately preventing APC/C mediated destruction. We wanted to test how transcript destabilization is impacted by this non-degradable Cyclin B3 using qRT-PCR. According to our model, we predict Cyclin B3 destruction is necessary for transcript destabilization, thus destabilization of transcripts will not occur with Cyclin B3-d. In addition to investigating Cyclin B3-d, we wanted to look at the effects of a *cort;cycB3* double mutant on transcript destabilization. Preliminary experiments show that transcript destabilization does occur in the absence of Cyclin B3 (Boruouh, 2018). Looking at our model, this can be explained by low Cdk1 activity in absence of Cyclin B3 leading to the PNG kinase complex being active. We predict that since this *cort;cycB3* double mutant should ultimately result in Cdk1 activity being low, PNG kinase will not be inhibited and thus the previously discussed downstream pathway of transcript destabilization occurs, despite the APC/C being inactive due to the *cort* mutant. If transcript destabilization does still occur in the double mutant, this model is most likely correct. Cortical microtubule reorganization will also be examined in the double mutant.

The final objective aimed to determine which technique was best for immunostaining cortical microtubules. Both methanol fixation and formaldehyde fixation techniques were meant to be investigated, each described in the materials and methods section. The two techniques will be used to stain wildtype and *cort* mutant embryos to compare which technique produced the best results.

Chapter 2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Gal4-UAS system

The two component Gal4-UAS system is used in these experiments to selectively express transgenes in the female germline. The Gal4-UAS system is natural machinery used by yeast to regulate gene expression. Historically, it has been a powerful tool for researchers to induce tissue specific expression of a given transgene. The yeast Gal4 transcription factor binds to regulator sites upstream of the gene, thus triggering transcription (Busson & Pret, 2007). These upstream regulatory sites contain a specific nucleotide sequence known as the upstream activating sequence, commonly referred to as the UAS (Busson & Pret, 2007). In *Drosophila*, the two components can be in different fly lines, thus allowing for a wide variety of combinations of inducible transgene expression. The germline specific Gal4 driver line used in these experiments is the *maternal α -tubulin-Gal4-67* and will be referred to as *mat67*. *mat67* triggers UAS transgene expression following pre-meiotic divisions and persists throughout oogenesis (Staller et al. 2013). The UAS transgenes used in these experiments are UAS-*GFPcycB3-d*, UAS-*fzy*^{RNAi}, and UAS-*APC3*^{RNAi}, which were all previously designed in our lab.

2.2 Crosses

The following crosses were performed to get the desired genotype denoted in bold. Numbered stocks are lab stocks. *CyO*, *s*, *Tm6*, and *Pr* are all balancer chromosomes. All females used in crosses were virgins. All crosses were performed at 25°C, with the exception of APC knockdown which was performed at 22°C. Yellow-white (*yw*) flies will serve as a wildtype control for all experiments.

Cort mutant:

$$\sigma \frac{cort^{RH}}{CyO}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr} \text{ (3.15)} \times \text{♀} \frac{cort^{QW}}{CyO}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr} \text{ (3.17)} \rightarrow \text{♀} \frac{cort^{RH}}{cort^{QW}}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr}$$

Balanced *cort*^{QW}; *cycB3*² stock:

$$\sigma \frac{cort^{QW}}{CyO}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr} (3.17) \times \text{♀} \frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{cycB3^2}{Tm6} \rightarrow \frac{cort^{QW}}{CyO}; \frac{cycB3^2}{Tm6}$$

Balanced *cycB3*^{L6} stock:

$$\sigma \frac{UAS GFPcycB3}{UAS GFPcycB3}; \frac{cycB3^{L6}}{Tm6} \times \text{♀} \frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr} (9.04) \rightarrow \sigma \frac{UAS GFPcycB3}{s}; \frac{cycB3^{L6}}{Tm6}$$

$$\sigma \frac{UAS GFPcycB3}{s}; \frac{cycB3^{L6}}{Tm6} \times \text{♀} \frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr} (9.04) \rightarrow \frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{cycB3^{L6}}{Tm6}$$

Balanced *cort*^{RH}; *cycB3*^{L6} stock:

$$\sigma \frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{cycB3^{L6}}{Tm6} \times \text{♀} \frac{cort^{RH}}{CyO}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr} (3.15) \rightarrow \frac{cort^{RH}}{CyO}; \frac{cycB3^{L6}}{Tm6}$$

cort; *cycB3* double mutant:

$$\sigma \frac{cort^{RH}}{CyO}; \frac{cycB3^{L6}}{Tm6} \times \text{♀} \frac{cort^{QW}}{CyO}; \frac{cycB3^2}{Tm6} \rightarrow \text{♀} \frac{cort^{RH}}{cort^{QW}}; \frac{cycB3^{L6}}{cycB3^2}$$

Fzy knockdown:

$$\text{♀} \frac{mat67}{mat67}; \frac{+}{+} \times \sigma \frac{+}{+}; \frac{UAS fzy^{RNAi(40933)}}{UAS fzy^{RNAi(40933)}} \rightarrow \text{♀} \frac{mat67}{+}; \frac{UAS fzy^{RNAi(40933)}}{+}$$

Balanced *FzyRNAi* stock (for future use):

$$\sigma \frac{+}{+}; \frac{UAS fzy^{RNAi(40933)}}{UAS fzy^{RNAi(40933)}} \times \text{♀} \frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr} (9.04) \rightarrow \sigma \frac{CyO}{+}; \frac{UAS fzy^{RNAi(40933)}}{Tm6}$$

$$\sigma \frac{CyO}{+}; \frac{UAS fzy^{RNAi(40933)}}{Tm6} \times \text{♀} \frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{Tm6}{Pr} (9.04) \rightarrow \frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{UAS fzy^{RNAi(40933)}}{Tm6}$$

APC knockdown:

$$\text{♀} \frac{\text{mat67}}{\text{mat67}}; \frac{+}{+} \times \text{♂} \frac{+}{+}; \frac{\text{UAS APC3}^{RNAi}}{\text{UAS APC3}^{RNAi}} \rightarrow \text{♀} \frac{\text{mat67}}{+}; \frac{\text{UAS APC3}^{RNAi}}{+}$$

Balanced *cycB3d* stock:

$$\text{♂} \frac{\text{UAS venus} \text{cycA}}{\text{cyo}}; \frac{\text{UAS GFPcycB3d}}{\text{Tm6}} (10.20) \times \text{♀} \frac{\text{CyO}}{\text{s}}; \frac{\text{Tm6}}{\text{Pr}} (9.04) \rightarrow \frac{\text{CyO}}{\text{s}}; \frac{\text{UAS GFPcycB3d}}{\text{Tm6}}$$

Expression of *cycB3d* from 10.20 stock:

$$\text{♀} \frac{\text{mat67}}{\text{mat67}}; \frac{+}{+} \times \text{♂} \frac{\text{CyO}}{\text{s}}; \frac{\text{UAS GFPcycB3d}}{\text{Tm6}} \rightarrow \text{♀} \frac{\text{mat67}}{\text{CyO/s}}; \frac{\text{UAS GFPcycB3d}}{+}$$

Expression of *cycB3d* from 10.17 stock:

$$\text{♀} \frac{\text{mat67}}{\text{mat67}}; \frac{+}{+} \times \text{♂} \frac{\text{CyO}}{\text{s}}; \frac{\text{pimdk1, UAS GFPcycB3d}}{\text{Tm6}} (10.17) \rightarrow \text{♀} \frac{\text{mat67}}{\text{CyO/s}}; \frac{\text{pimdk1, UAS GFPcycB3d}}{+}$$

2.3 Sample Preparation for Western Blot

Ovaries were dissected in 1X PBS. Following dissection, they were transferred to Eppendorf tube, flash froze in liquid nitrogen then ground in 20 μ L of 2X SB per pair of ovaries, followed by boiling of the sample at 65 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 minutes. They were then stored at -20 $^{\circ}$ C until ready to use.

2.4 Western Blot Protocol

10 μ L of each sample was loaded into a 7.5% polyacrylamide gel and ran at 120 V. The transfer to a nitrocellulose membrane using 350 mA current for 1 hour. The nitrocellulose membrane was stained in Ponceau Red for 5 minutes. Blocking was done using 5% milk solution in TBST for 1 hour. The membrane was then sealed in a hybridization bag with 1/1000 Rabbit anti-GFP IgG primary antibody

(Torrey Pines Biolabs, Lot: 081211) in TBST and left to incubate overnight. Following TBST washing, the CyTM5 AffiniPureTM Goat Anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) secondary antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories Inc.) was added at 1/10000 for 1 hour. The blot was then washed in TBST and imaged using SuperSignal West Pico Plus Chemiluminescent Substrate and imaged using BIORAD ChemiDec Imaging System.

2.5 Bacterial Transformation and Plasmid Isolation

0.05 mL of NEB 5-alpha Competent *E. coli* cells (New England BioLabs) were transformed with pUAS-GFPcycB3dSDM plasmid according to NEB 5-alpha Competent *E. coli* High Efficiency transformation protocol, with the exception of using 2TY media rather than SOC. 1 mL was added to a LB-amp selection plates and spread using a plate spreader. Using a sterilized plate spreader, the initial spread-out aliquot was spread to a second LB-amp plate. Both plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C, then wrapped in parafilm and stored ~48 hours at 4 °C. Using a pipette tip, four individual colonies were selected, two from each the diluted and non-diluted plate. The pipette tip was then added to an autoclaved glass vial containing 2 mL of 2TY media and 4 µL of filter sterilized 100mg/mL ampicillin solution and incubated overnight at 37 °C in a 220 rpm shaker. The following day, the plasmid was isolated using Qiagen QIAprep Spin Miniprep kit. The plasmid concentration following isolation was measured using the Thermo Scientific NanoDrop OneC Microvolume UV-Vis Spectrophotometer. The plasmid concentration of the chosen colony was 385.4 ng/µL and the 260/280 value was 1.90. (The 260/280 value is a ratio of absorbance of the sample at 260 nm light to absorbance at 280 nm light, indicative of nucleic acid purity).

2.6 Restriction Digest

The restriction digest contained 0.3 μL each of EcoRI and EcoRV restriction endonucleases, 1 μL of buffer, and variable amounts of DNA plasmid and nuclease free water for a reaction volume of 10 μL with 1 μg DNA. Reaction was carried out at 37 degrees for 1 hr. 2 μL DNA loading dye was then added into each of the restriction digest tubes. Each sample was run on a 1% agarose gel (containing 5 μL of ethidium bromide) at 120 V until the dye front showed sufficient migration. The gel was then imaged using the BIORAD ChemiDoc MP imaging system.

2.7 Embryo Collections

Flies were placed in egg laying chamber on apple juice agar plates with dried yeast solution. The egg laying chamber was at 25°C, with the exception of APC knockdown which was kept at 22°C. The plates were changed no longer than 48 hours apart. For embryo collection, the plates were swapped with a fresh new pre-lay plate. Following 1 hour with the pre-lay plate, the pre-lay was removed and a new plate was added for a 2-hour time interval. Following the 2-hour interval, embryos were collected immediately for 0–2-hour samples, or the plate was placed at 25°C for an additional 3 hours for 3–5-hour samples. Embryos were then rinsed with bleach and poured into an embryo basket, rinsed with water, then rinsed with embryo wash, rinsed again with water, and then placed in embryo wash. Embryos were transferred to Eppendorf tube and embryo wash was removed by pipette. The samples were either flash frozen with liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C or fixed in methanol or formaldehyde (described below).

2.8 RNA Extraction

RNA extraction and purification was carried out using the Qiagen RNeasy Mini Kit. Although, there was large amount of variability, roughly 10-20 μL of embryos was used for each RNA extraction.

RNA concentration was measured using the Thermo Scientific NanoDrop OneC Microvolume UV-Vis Spectrophotometer. The results of each extraction used for cDNA synthesis is listed below:

Sample	RNA concentration (ng/ μ L)	260/280
yw 0-2	26.5	2.07
yw 3-5	63.9	2.16
Fzy 0-2 (1 st replicate)	147.2	2.17
Fzy 3-5 (1 st replicate)	76.5	2.36
Fzy 0-2 (2 nd replicate)	69.5	2.13
Fzy 3-5 (2 nd replicate)	21.3	1.94

2.9 cDNA Synthesis

The Thermo Scientific RevertAid First Strand cDNA Synthesis kit was used to make cDNA from purified RNA. Each cDNA reaction was adjusted that each reaction would have between 0.20 and 0.25 μ g of RNA. The reaction took place at 42 °C for 1 hour, followed by termination at 70 °C for 5 minutes. The cDNA was then stored at -80 °C.

2.10 qRT-PCR

Two master mixes were made with SYBR Green reagent, one for control gene (*rpa1*) and one for target gene (*nanos*). Each master mix consisted of 80 μ L of SYBR Green, 6.4 μ L of 5 uM forward and reverse primers for *rpa1* or *nanos*. cDNA of each sample was diluted to 1/5 in nuclease-free water. The reactions were carried out in 384 well plate so that each reaction received 5.6 μ L of SYBR + primer master mix, and 4.6 μ L of diluted cDNA of each sample, or 4 μ L of nuclease-free water as a negative control. Each reaction was performed in triplicate. The reaction was performed in the Thermo Fischer Viiia 7 Real-Time PCR System.

2.11 Methanol Fixation of Embryos

600 μ L of heptane was added to Eppendorf tube containing the embryos, followed immediately by 600 μ L of methanol and then shook vigorously by hand for ~10-15 seconds. Heptane and most

methanol were removed. Another 600 μ L of methanol was added, mixed, removed, then repeated one more time. The embryos were stored at -20°C in ~ 600 μ L of methanol.

2.12 Immunostaining of Methanol Fixed Embryos

Following methanol fixation, embryos were gradually rehydrated and then blocked in a 1% BSA solution in PBST for ~ 1 hour at room temperature. The embryos were then incubated overnight at 4°C followed by 1 hour at room temperature in PBST containing Thermo Fisher Scientific Invitrogen alpha Tubulin Monoclonal Antibody (YL1/2, Lot: XB3238702A) at 1/1000, RNase A (1/250) and 1% BSA. After incubation, embryos were rinsed and washed in fresh 1X PBST. The CyTM3 AffiniPureTM Goat Anti-Rat IgG (H+L) secondary antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories Inc.) was then added (1/1000) with OliGreen (1/500) in 1% BSA and PBST. Rinsing and washing in PBST followed overnight at incubation 4°C . The embryos were then incubated with methanol for 5 minutes, then isopropanol for 10 minutes. Isopropanol was removed and 60 μ L of tetrahydronaphthalene was added to embryos that were subsequently mounted on glass slides and sealed with nail polish. The slides were stored at 4°C until imaging.

2.13 Formaldehyde Fixation of Embryos

A fixative solution was prepared using 600 μ L heptane, 540 μ L PBST, 60 μ L of 37% formaldehyde, and 1 μ L EGTA (ethylene glycol-bis-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid). This solution was mixed and added to embryos where it was fixed on a nutator for 10 minutes, then removed. Another 600 μ L of heptane was added, followed immediately by 600 μ L of methanol and then shook vigorously by hand for ~ 60 seconds. Heptane and most methanol were removed, along with embryos at the interface. Another 600 μ L of methanol was added, mixed, removed, then repeated one more time. The embryos were stored at -20°C in ~ 600 μ L of methanol.

2.14 Immunostaining of Formaldehyde Fixed Embryos

Immunostaining was done analogously to staining of methanol embryos described in Section 2.12, with the exception of using Anti-histone, H1+core proteins mouse monoclonal, clone F152.C25.WJJ (Millipore Sigma, Lot: 2465294) primary antibody at 1/1000 in place of Oligreen and RNase A.

Chapter 3 Results

3.1 Transcript Destabilization in Fzy Knockdown

Destabilization of maternally deposited mRNA transcripts is a process of activation that occurs during the 3–5-hour time interval following egg laying. One of the well-known mRNA transcripts that undergo this destabilization is *nanos*, which is used in these experiments as the experimental transcript (Tadros et al., 2003). *rpa1* is a mRNA transcript which remains at relatively constant levels in embryos, thus is used as the control transcript (Tadros et al., 2003). To test our proposed model and replicate previous findings, *nanos* mRNA levels in 0-2 hour and 3-5 hour time interval were analysed relative to *rpa1* mRNA using qRT-PCR. *yw* is a wildtype control.

Our model suggests that Fzy is required for transcript destabilization. Fzy is an activator of the APC/C required to lower Cdk1 activity hypothesized to be necessary for transcript destabilization, such that PNG kinase becomes active. Results of the qRT-PCR of the *fzy* knockdown are seen below in Figure 2. Each qRT-PCR reaction was preformed in triplicate. The data suggests that transcript destabilization is Fzy dependant, since *nanos* transcripts are stable in the 3-5 hour time interval. This result nicely agrees with preliminary data by Boruouh, 2018, and our proposed model such that Fzy is necessary for transcript destabilization. Interestingly, *nanos* transcript levels are noticeably increased in the 3-5 hour time interval; the significance of this is discussed in detail in the discussion section. The large standard deviation in the three triplicates for the wildtype control 0-2 hour embryos is noted, and is something that needs to be redone in the future. The data analysis from the qRT-PCR results was preformed by Rajni.

Figure 2. mRNA levels in *fzy* knockdown examined using qRT-PCR. Relative *nanos* mRNA levels relative to wildtype control (*yw*). The *fzy* knockdown sample shows stable transcript levels in the 3-5 hour time interval compared to *yw* embryos aged 3-5 hours, which supports that Fzy is required for transcript destabilization. Data is from a single experiment, each qRT-PCR reaction was formed in triplicate.

In addition to transcript destabilization, *fzy* embryos have been fixed in methanol and immunostained to look at cortical microtubule reorganization. We are waiting for access to the confocal microscope to view these embryos. Wildtype control staining is also something that needs to be done in order to make a comparison.

3.2 APC/C Knockdown

Preliminary data from Boruouh, 2018 found that when a subunit of the APC/C is knocked down using RNA interference, transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization do not occur,

suggesting that both processes are APC/C dependant. Regarding our model for transcript destabilization, we propose that APC/C mediated ubiquitination of Cyclin B3 is necessary for inactivation of Cdk1. This drop in Cdk1 activity would allow for PNG kinase to transition to an active state. When APC/C is knocked down, ubiquitination of Cyclin B3 would not occur, therefore Cdk1 would remain active. Cdk1 activity will cause PNG kinase to remain phosphorylated and inactive, therefore unable to phosphorylate the downstream target required for transcript destabilization.

Unfortunately, repeated fertility was observed in the flies that should have had a subunit of the APC/C knocked down via UAS- *APC3*^{RNAi} germline expression. The observed fertility can be interpreted as that there is no RNA interference occurring. The cross is currently being repeated one final time on a small scale to test if the stock is useful. Testing another stock ($\frac{UAS\ GFP}{CyO}; \frac{UAS\ APC3RNAi}{Tm6}$) to see if sterility is observed is also something being done currently.

3.3 Non-Degradable Cyclin B3

Expressing a non-degradable Cyclin B3 in the female germline was initially a goal of this research. This non degradable Cyclin B3, Cyclin B3-d, was previously designed in our lab using site directed mutagenesis. We predicted that since Cyclin B3 levels will stay elevated, Cdk1-Cyclin B3 activity will remain high, thus PNG kinase will remain inhibited, such that transcript destabilization will not occur.

Germline expression of Cyclin B3-d should result in sterility; their eggs should not hatch into larvae. However, repeated trials of two different stocks continuously yielded fertile females. Both a western blot and genomic prep analysis was done using the 10.20 ($\frac{UAS\ venuscyca}{cyo}; \frac{UAS\ GFPcycB3d}{Tm6}$) stock to test for the presence of the transgene. Both showed no evidence of CyclinB3-d, however lacked the necessary positive controls to make a definitive conclusion. Despite a definitive result, the 10.17

$\left(\frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{pimdK1, UAS\ GFPcycB3d}{Tm6}\right)$ stock was tested instead. Figure 3 shows the western blot performed on dissected ovarian tissue of flies that were supposed to be expressing the transgene from the 10.17 stock. The results showed no reason to believe the transgene was being expressed.

Figure 3. Western blot to confirm absence of GFP-Cyclin B3-d. Ponceau red stain of nitrocellulose membrane (left), chemiluminescence of western blot (middle), and ladder used for western blot (right). The expected band size of GFP-Cyclin B3-d from the 10.17 stock is ~95 kDa, which was concluded to be absent.

Given that both 10.20 and 10.17 were presumed to be not useful, the next step was to transform competent *E. coli* cells with the pUAS-*GFPcycB3dSDM* plasmid such that the plasmid could be purified and sent away for microinjection. Following transformation and purification of the plasmid, a restriction digest using *EcoRI* and *EcoRV* restriction endonucleases to confirm the identity of the isolated genetic material. The plasmid should yield DNA fragments of 7008 bp, 2888 bp, and 2450 bp. The results of the restriction digest are seen in Figure 4. Colonies 1,2, and 4 all showed anticipated band size. Colony 2 was chosen to be sent away for microinjection.

A)

Sequence: pUASp-AXN Range: 1 to 12346

Digest with EcoRI, EcoRV:

Fragment Size	Left Overhang	Cut by Enzyme	From : To	Cut by Enzyme	Right Overhang
7008	[+ 4]	EcoRI	2370:9377	EcoRV	[+ 0]
2888	[+ 0]	EcoRV	9378:12265	EcoRV	[+ 0]
2450	[+ 0]	EcoRV	12266:2369	EcoRI	[+ 4]

B)

Figure 4. EcoRI and EcoRV restriction digest of purified pUAS-*GFPcycB3dSDM* plasmid. A) Restriction digest map and expected band size. B) Results of the restriction digest, showing expected band size in 3 of the 4 colonies.

The flies following microinjection have been received recently. Rajni is currently conducting subsequent crosses with the aim of obtaining a new stock that carries the non-degradable Cyclin B3 transgene so that transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization can be investigated in the presence of a non-degradable Cyclin B3.

3.4 *cort*; *cycB3* Double Mutant

Transcript destabilization when a functional Cort and Cyclin B3 protein is absent is a crucial component that needed to be tested to confirm our proposed model is correct. We predict that phosphorylation of the PNG kinase complex mediated by Cdk1 activity will not occur due to the absence of functional Cyclin B3, therefore PNG kinase will be unphosphorylated and thus active, despite the APC/C being inactive due to lack of a functional Cort protein.

Generating balanced stocks that had the respective mutant alleles necessary to ultimately achieve *cort*;*cycB3* double mutants was something that took nearly the entire duration of this project. Offspring from the final cross are currently being screened for the correct genotype. Following embryo collection from the double mutants, both transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization will be experimentally examined.

The cross will also yield offspring that are single mutants of either *cort* or *cycB3*. *Cort* mutants fail to undergo both transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization, thus will serve nicely as positive controls (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996; Lieberfarb et al., 1996; Boruouh, 2018). Transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization will be examined in the *cycB3* mutants to validate and confirm early findings by Boruouh, 2018 that both phenomena do occur in *cycB3* mutants.

3.5 Microtubule Reorganization of *cort* Mutant to Determine Best Technique

Cortical microtubule reorganization is a crucial phenomenon of egg activation. *cort* mutants fail to undergo this reorganization (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996). The staining of *cort* mutant embryos was done to establish a positive control and determine if methanol fixation or formaldehyde fixation was the best technique for future experiments. Each technique is described in the methods section. Figure 5

shows a *cort* mutant embryo fixed in methanol. Rajni helped visualize the embryos using the confocal microscope. Unfortunately, this result is rather meaningless since there were no wildtype comparison and such low sample numbers. Samples fixed in formaldehyde were lost due to contaminated PBST solution, and hence this is something that should be tested in the future with proper controls.

Figure 5. *cort* mutant fixed in methanol. 0-2 hour aged *cort* mutant embryos fixed in methanol and stained using OliGreen DNA dye and anti-tubulin primary antibody visualized using confocal microscope. No interpretation can be made from these results due to the absence of a wildtype control.

Chapter 4 Discussion:

4.1 Fzy Knockdown

Our model suggests that Fzy binds to and activates the APC/C. This activity of the APC/C is necessary for destruction of Cyclin B3 which ultimately allows for transcript destabilization. The results of the Fzy knockdown on transcript destabilization agree both with preliminary data and our model. Figure 2 shows *nanos* mRNA is stable in the *fzy* knockdown 3–5-hour embryos compared to wildtype during that same time interval. While the standard deviation on the *yw* 0-2-hour sample is extremely large, this is most likely attributed to simple loading errors; nevertheless, it should be repeated.

Interestingly, *nanos* transcript levels actually increased in the 3–5-hour interval as seen in Figure 2. This is something that was also seen by Boruouh, 2018. The increased transcript levels was something that was seen exclusively in the *fzy* knockdown. *Cort* mutants, and a mutant subunit of the APC/C both showed stabilized transcript levels in the 3-5 hour interval; however, they were roughly the same or slightly lower compared to the 0-2 hour aged embryos (Boruouh, 2018). Logically, this result for *fzy* knockdown is confusing since wildtype embryos aged 3-5-hours have extremely low levels of *nanos* mRNA, so how could transcript levels increase in the 3-5-hour embryos compared to 0-2 hour embryos when *fzy* was knocked down? This absolutely should be an area of investigation in subsequent studies.

Additionally, *fzy* knockdown embryos have been fixed in methanol and underwent microtubule staining have been prepared in slides, however have yet to be viewed. No conclusion can be made on Fzy's role in microtubule reorganization until proper positive and negative controls are examined.

4.2 APC/C Knockdown

This project aimed to replicate and validate previous findings by Boruouh, 2018 that the APC/C is required for transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization. For transcript

destabilization, we predict that since Cyclin B3 is unable to get degraded via APC/C ubiquitination, Cdk1-Cyclin B3 activity will remain high, thus keeping PNG kinase inactive. This inactive PNG kinase would not be able to phosphorylate TRAL, thus ultimately transcript destabilization would not occur. In a similar fashion to the Cyclin B3-d transgene, after crossing UAS- *APC3^{RNAi}* flies to *mat67* on two different occasions, the offspring were not sterile both times, indicating that the UAS- *APC3^{RNAi}* transgene is not present. This cross is currently being repeated on a small scale to test if there is any evidence that the transgene is present in the homozygous stock. Additionally, another stock ($\frac{UAS\ GFP}{cyO}; \frac{UAS\ APC3RNAi}{Tm6}$) is being tested to see if sterility is observed in the offspring when crossed with *mat67*.

4.3 Non-Degradable Cyclin B3

Investigating transcript destabilization through the utilization of flies expressing a germline Cyclin B3 mutant lacking a functional D-box, rendering it non-degradable, was initially a critical goal of this project. We predict that since Cyclin B3 levels will stay elevated, Cdk1-Cyclin B3 activity will remain high, and the PNG kinase will remain inhibited.

After making a balanced stock from the 10.20 stock ($\frac{UAS\ venusycyA}{cyo}; \frac{UAS\ GFPcycB3d}{Tm6}$), male flies were crossed to *mat67* female virgins. The offspring, after screening for the right genotype, should have both *mat67* expression and the *cycB3-d* gene downstream of the UAS sequence, hence the non-degradable Cyclin B3 should be expressed and therefore would cause the females to be sterile. However, this was not the case. The females were indeed not sterile, and their eggs hatched. After remaking a balanced stock two more times and crossing each of the newly formed stocks to *mat67* females, once again no sterility was observed. This led to the suspicion that the *cycB3-d* transgene was not present. Both a western blot and genomic prep analysis was done using the 10.20 stock. Both showed no

evidence of GFP-CyclinB3d, however lacked the necessary positive controls to make a definitive conclusion at the time. Despite lacking definitive evidence that the desired transgene was not present, there was enough evidence via repeated fertility to suggest that cyclin B3d was not present in the 10.20 stock.

The 10.17 stock $\left(\frac{CyO}{s}; \frac{pimdK1, UAS\ GFP_{cycB3d}}{Tm6}\right)$ was crossed with *mat67*, as discussed in methods section, and the offspring were once again not sterile. This cross was repeated an additional two times with the same outcome of non-sterile offspring. To confirm that the transgene was absent in this stock, another western blot was performed with the 10.17 stock. The expected size of GFP-Cyclin B3-d is approximately 95 kDa. No band was observed in the 10.17 lane, whereas a strong band was observed in the positive control lane, as seen in Figure 3. Despite this being strong evidence, it can be seen in the Ponceau stain, Figure 3A, that there were clear loading differences in the positive control lane compared to the other two lanes. This questions the validity of the experiment to make a definitive conclusion but coupled with the evidence of no sterility repeatedly being observed, it was a reasonable assumption to make that Cyclin B3d was not present in the 10.17 stock.

Given that the two Cyclin B3d lab stocks were both assumed to be not useful, we transformed competent *E. coli* with pUAS-*GFP_{cycB3d}*SDM plasmid so that the plasmid could be purified and sent for microinjection. Following transformation, the plasmid was isolated, and a restriction digest was done to confirm the identity of the genetic material. As seen in Figure 4, three out of four selected colonies showed band sizes corresponding to the expected sizes. The plasmid from colony 2 was chosen to be sent away for microinjection.

We recently received the flies following microinjection. The flies are currently being crossed by Rajni, with hopes to get a new stock containing the UAS-*GFP_{cycB3-d}* transgene. Hopefully transcript

destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization in embryos expressing a non-degradable form of Cyclin B3 can be experimentally determined in future investigations.

4.4 *cort;cycB3* Double Mutant

The *cort;cycB3* double mutant is something that is crucial to test our proposed model of transcript destabilization. We propose that APC/C activation is necessary to degrade Cyclin B3. This leads to a drop in Cdk1 activity so that the PNG kinase can transition to an active state. Cort is a germline specific activator of the APC/C in female meiosis. *cort* mutants fail to undergo transcript destabilization (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996; Lieberfarb et al., 1996; Boruouh, 2018). Transcript destabilization does occur in *cycB3* mutants which can be explained by low Cdk1 activity allowing PNG kinase to remain active, although this is still considered preliminary (Boruouh, 2018). Therefore, we predict that the low Cdk1 activity in the double mutant will allow PNG kinase to remain unphosphorylated, despite the APC/C being inactive due to the *cort* mutant. If transcript destabilization still occurs in the *cort;cycB3* double mutant, it can be considered strong evidence that our proposed model is correct.

Generating necessary balanced stocks to ultimately achieve the double mutant is a process that extended the duration of nearly this entire project, but was achieved successfully. The offspring of the final cross are currently being screened for the correct genotype, and *cort;cycB3* double mutant females are being collected. Embryo collection followed by either microtubule staining or RNA extraction, cDNA synthesis, and qRT-PCR to examine transcript destabilization is something that will be done in the near future.

4.5 Determination of Best Technique for Microtubule Staining

Investigating the success of formaldehyde fixing compared to methanol fixation for looking at cortical microtubule reorganization is something that was supposed to be done. Ideally, the two techniques would have been used to stain *yw* and *cort* mutant embryos to compare which technique produced the best results. *cort* mutants fail to undergo cortical microtubule reorganization, hence would have served as a positive control (Page & T.L. Orr-Weaver, 1996). Unfortunately, due to loss of samples when preparing slides and using contaminated PBST solution, we were unable to look at the success of cortical microtubule staining following formaldehyde fixation. *cort* mutant embryos fixed in methanol are shown in Figure 5 but are essentially meaningless with such a small sample number and nothing to compare them to. Therefore, determination of the best technique is something that still needs to be done.

4.6 Conclusions and Additional Future Steps

The result of transcript levels to investigate transcript destabilization in the *fzy* knockdown embryos is very promising and validates preliminary data (Boruouh, 2018). Further repeats of this experiment are needed to make a definitive conclusion that Fzy is required for transcript destabilization following egg activation. Additionally, investigating why *nanos* mRNA is increased in 3-5-hour *fzy* knockdown embryos compared to 0-2 hour embryos is something that should be explored in the future. The APC/C knockdown is still a work in progress, but hopefully we can ultimately validate preliminary findings of transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization soon.

The non-degradable Cyclin B3 and *cort;cycB3* double mutant experiments has yet to be preformed, yet promising steps have been made through the duration of this project. Investigating the role of other mitotic/meiotic cyclins, namely Cyclin A and Cyclin B, in transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization is also something that should be done later on.

Observing the phosphorylation states of PNG kinase in the various mutants and knockdowns is also something that should be done in future experiments to further validate our model. Active PNG kinase is ultimately required for transcript destabilization (Hara et al., 2017). The phosphorylation state of GNU, one of the subunits of the PNG kinase complex, determines whether the enzyme is active or inactive. Phosphorylated and unphosphorylated GNU migrates differently in a western blot, therefore we can use antibodies against GNU to observe phosphorylation states for all previously discussed mutants and RNAi knockdowns. For example, in the *fzy* knockdown we predict that since the APC/C will not be activated by Fzy, Cyclin B3 will not be ubiquitinated hence Cdk1 activity will remain high. High Cdk1 activity will lead to GNU being phosphorylated and thus inhibited. The phosphorylation state of GNU would be determined using western blotting. Ultimately, determining the phosphorylation states of PNG kinase in each discussed genotype would provide further support to our proposed model.

Overall, this project made good progress in better understanding two key events of activation: transcript destabilization and cortical microtubule reorganization. The majority of this project is still being carried out with hope to better understand the role of Cort, Fzy, APC/C, and Cyclin B3 in *Drosophila* egg activation.

Statement of Contribution

All work in this thesis was performed by myself, unless otherwise noted. This project was carried out as part of Rajni's project, a PhD student of Dr. Andrew Swan's Lab at the University of Windsor.

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